

Executive Summary

Exploring the Use of Virtual Reality for Professional Teaching and Learning in Complex Social Situations

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Background

Virtual reality (VR) has become an increasingly accessible tool for professional education, driven by developments in consumer headsets and interactive simulation technology. While VR is widely used for technical and procedural training, such as surgical engineering and military simulations,^{1,3} it is less clear whether immersive VR is suitable for developing complex social skills required in professional contexts. Such learning involves interpreting interpersonal cues, managing emotions, engaging in communication, and making context-dependent judgements⁴. These competencies are particularly relevant to fields such as teaching, healthcare, counselling, and intercultural communication.

Although recent work identifies VR's potential to support affective and interpersonal skill development⁵, a systematic evaluation of how VR is being designed and implemented for socially complex vocational learning is lacking. This review aims to examine whether immersive VR is a feasible medium for professional learning in scenarios requiring complex social understanding.

Research Questions

1. **Design:** How are VR experiences being designed to support learning of complex social situations?
2. **Effectiveness:** How effective are these VR experiences in facilitating learning?
3. **Learner Response:** How do participants respond to VR as a learning tool?

Methods

Following PRISMA⁺ guidelines⁶, searches were conducted across Scopus, EBSCO, Medline and Web of Science. Eligibility criteria were defined using the SPIDER framework⁷. Studies were included if they:

- Used immersive VR as defined by contemporary VR guidelines⁸;
- Targeted professional or vocational learning;
- Addressed complex social, affective, or interpersonal skills;
- Reported empirical data.

Studies relying solely on 360° video, desktop-based “low immersive” environments, or empathy-only experiences without measurable learning outcomes were excluded.

Of 1,422 records, nine studies met the full criteria. These spanned healthcare (n=6), cultural communication (n=1), and teacher education (n=2). Quality appraisal using CASP⁺ and JBI⁺ tools^{12,13} indicated moderate to high overall study quality.

Key Findings

1. Design of VR Learning Experiences

Design decisions were varied and inconsistently reported, limiting comparability across studies.

- **Hardware and software:** Most studies used consumer-grade head mounted devices such as Oculus Rift or HTC Vive. However, only a subset specified development engines (commonly Unity3D)⁹, while several gave no software details. This lack of reporting constrains replicability and understanding of learner experience.
- **Pedagogical frameworks:** Few studies explicitly described their pedagogical grounding. Some applied constructivist or experiential frameworks^{9,10}, while others relied implicitly on practice-based learning, repetition, or narrative immersion¹¹. The absence of clear theoretical development is a notable limitation.
- **Fidelity and realism:** Across studies, learners emphasised the importance of realism through graphical fidelity¹², cognitive fidelity¹³, and avatar behaviour¹⁴. Although avatar-based interactions were central in most studies, participants frequently noted limitations in expressiveness or motion quality.
- **Design challenges:** Common issues included high development complexity and cost¹⁵, discomfort for some participants (e.g., glasses users)¹⁶, and constraints on session length due to cybersickness¹⁶.

Overall, design choices significantly shaped presence, emotional engagement, and perceived authenticity, underscoring the need for transparent reporting and theoretically grounded development frameworks.

2. Effectiveness for Learning Complex Social Skills

Across the reviewed studies, VR had consistently positive effects on learning outcomes.

- **Skill development:** Pre-post and controlled studies showed improvements in communication, teamwork, cultural awareness, counselling skills, and recognition of complex social cues^{11,17-19}. In controlled designs, VR learners frequently outperformed those using traditional methods.
- **Mechanisms of learning:** Although rarely articulated directly, evidence suggests embodied perspective-taking²⁰, heightened affective arousal²¹, and narrative engagement²² may contribute to learning. Some studies showed VR to be more effective than conventional methods for emotional and cognitive restructuring²³.
- **Limitations:** Research is concentrated in just a few fields and uses small samples, making generalisation difficult. There is limited longitudinal data on skill retention or diminishing novelty effects.

Despite these limitations, findings strongly suggest that immersive VR can enhance learning in socially complex vocational scenarios.

3. Learner Experiences and Responses

Participants' responses to VR-based learning were positive.

- **Engagement and presence:** Learners reported strong immersion, focused attention, and high engagement²⁴⁻²⁶. Many described VR as more stimulating and effective than reading, lectures, or online modules.
- **Perspective-taking and empathy:** Participants valued opportunities to take alternative viewpoints and reflect on emotional and interpersonal situations^{27,28}. In teacher-education studies, learners reported increased empathy and improved awareness of bullying-related cues¹⁰.
- **Usability and satisfaction:** Most studies reported high usability and satisfaction ratings²⁹. However, issues such as headset discomfort and occasional interface awkwardness were noted.
- **Novelty bias:** Several studies acknowledged novelty effects³⁰. In some cases, participants still preferred traditional interpersonal instruction, suggesting VR should supplement rather than replace established methods.

Overall, findings indicate that VR can support reflection, creativity, collaboration, and complex social reasoning.

Conclusions and Implications

This systematic review provides the first cross-disciplinary synthesis of immersive VR applications for learning complex social skills in vocational environments. The evidence demonstrates that VR is a promising and feasible medium for developing communication, empathy, reflective practice, and decision-making in socially complex scenarios.

However, progress is limited by inconsistent design reporting, narrow disciplinary scope, and dependence on small samples. To advance the field, future research should:

- Adopt explicit pedagogical frameworks and detailed design descriptions;
- Standardise reporting of hardware and software choices;
- Conduct longitudinal research to assess retention and novelty effects;
- Broaden applications across professional domains;
- Investigate how simulated environments support social cognition.

VR offers a safe, repeatable, and highly controllable environment for exploring complex professional situations. With improved methodological rigour and theoretical grounding, it has significant potential to strengthen vocational learning in socially demanding fields.

* PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Inventory for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

^ CASP: Critical Appraisal

+ JBI: Joanna Briggs Institute

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